

Effectiveness of Social Media Platform among DOT Accredited Resort Hotels in Tagaytay City

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Abstract: Social media has witnessed exponential growth in the new millennium and the present information has contributed a wide variation of marketing in the hospitality industry that has quite the spotlight on hotels and restaurants. The effectiveness of social media has varied a lot of unique and strategized formation of promotions, preview, and branding towards specific hotels. The research would assess the effectiveness of social media platforms among accredited DOT (Department of Tourism) Hotels in Tagaytay based on Quality/Content of post, User Experience, and People Reached. The study is using Correlational Quantitative and used a 4-point Likert scale method and the prior respondents are the hotels' previous guests. The researchers chose Dependent and Independent for the theoretical framework. The researchers had provided survey questionnaires to 323 respondents and the study's results show that most of the guests who are prone to book for hotels are at the age of 18-26, female with a detailed elaboration of hotels intended to book for mostly leisure and the nationalities are mostly Filipino.

Keywords: Accredited, Quality / Content of Post, User Experience, People Reached, Accommodation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social Media nowadays has been a big help to everybody's lives since it makes everything handy and easy. It connects people even from the other side of the world and connections or communications have never been this easy with one click of the mouse. Thus, as years pass, many internet users are prone to exposure to social media that they were influenced to decide on what trends or what acts they would partake in to do a particular movement. According to the study of Vasudeva Akula (2017), social media is a wide variation of platforms that greatly affects and influences an individual based on its capability to influence others and what data or information it gathers and considering as social media data is a valuable and timely information source of input for making certain decisions. It has made lives easy because we can do everything in just one sitting--we can do our studies and surf the net, we can start our own business with just our laptop and the internet as our starting points or it can be used to organize events and showcase opinions that a wider audience can view. We can socialize, find information, and share everything through social media, and post content about everything and connect. It exposes our daily lives to a new level as to share our lives with people who half the time visit our profile are strangers--thus we must keep vigilant and aware as to who we are sharing this information when it's posted on social media and it has been part of our daily routine (Siddiqui & Singh, 2016). Merriam-Webster defines social media as "forms of electronic communication in which users create online communities to share information, ideas and content" (Merriam Webster, n.d.)

The way the consumers and companies communicate and connect around the world with the Internet having a large contribution—amidst the geographical and time constraints (Verma, 2018). She also stated that there are various changes in technology and are now performed through a new platform of communication known as social media. The increase in the use of technology and social media has resulted in the development of the tourism and hospitality industry (Benea,

2014). Consumers now use social media for connecting people from different destinations, deciding which hotel to stay, and purchasing the offered travel services and products (Varkaris & Neuhofer, 2017). Using the effectiveness of social media to connect and promote the tourism and hospitality industry as an advertisement could have its disadvantages if done wrong. An advertisement is deceiving, false, or spurious if it doesn't conform with the provision of Republic Act 7394. The advertisement may be determined as fallacious if it fails to represent or reveal the true intent of the purpose of the advertisement as a result of the wrong usage of the consumer to the platforms presented. (Republic Act 7394, 1992).

Research shows that social media has been one of the most used platforms in the Philippines other than other media sources in our country. For the past year's hotels have been mostly advertising on billboards, magazines, TV commercials, and only some are only found on Social Media and if there are, it was not too noticeable. The researchers chose this subject to analyze how social media can be an effective platform in increasing the clients of hotels. The researchers have chosen Tagaytay as the basis and location of the study because it is a very accessible and convenient place if one is looking for a high-rating hotel. Tagaytay has been a tourist destination because of the ridge overlooking the famous Taal Volcano. It has rolling hills and great scenery and the climate could drop to 13C during Christmas months because of the cultivation of trees around. It houses high-rating hotels. Tagaytay is in upland and people are most likely to unwind and spend time relaxing, it houses high-rated accredited resort hotels which was named as Hotel A, Hotel B, and Hotel C Tagaytay because mostly the tourists in Tagaytay usually stay there for only a weekend and travelers today want a deeper connection with the places they visit. According to the official site of Cavite Province, these resort hotels are some hotels that are accredited by the Department of Tourism in the CALABARZON Region (*Department of Tourism (DOT) accredited tourism establishments, n.d.*).

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig 1: Dependent and Independent Model

The researchers used the Independent and Dependent Variable framework to determine the effectiveness of social media adapted from the study of Makina & Kengara (2018). The framework maps the relationship between the dependent variables such as the Quality of content of the posts, User Experience, People Reached, and the Accredited Hotels. The dependent variables are the variables wherein it can be changed depending on the responses of the participants and it determines the guests who book the hotels through the means of Social Media which determines how effective social media is to guests. The independent variable which is the standalone variable and is the accredited hotel and significantly affected by the dependent variable by way of user reviews and opinions.

Statement of the Problem

The study aims to determine the effectiveness of social media platforms specifically Facebook and Instagram from the previous guests of Hotel A, Hotel B, Hotel C. The proponents assessed how effective social media is in their booking decisions and how they can improve their online engagements.

Specifically, the study will answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Nationality

- 1.4 Purpose of stay
- 1.5 Income per annual
- 1.6 Time spent on social media
2. How will the respondents assess the effectiveness of social media in terms of:
 - 2.1 Quality or content of the posts
 - 2.2 User Experiences
 - 2.3 People Reached
3. Is there a significant relationship between the factors (quality of post, user experiences and people reached) that measures the effectiveness of social media?
4. Based on the results, what recommendations can be proposed to the hotels to improve their social media presence to encourage more potential guests and or clients?

Statement of Hypothesis

The statement of the null hypothesis in this study will be: There is no significant relationship between the factors (quality of post, user experiences and people reached) that measure the effectiveness of social media.

Research Objectives

The general objective of this study is to determine the overall impact and effectiveness of social media platforms to guests. Specifically, this study would like to determine the effectiveness of social media in influencing and molding the preferences and decisions of the past guests and from the potential guests of the specified hotels. Furthermore, this was to help the hoteliers market or attract guests through their social media and increase their online presence with the goal of reaching more potential guests and clients.

Review of Related Literature

Social media has replaced brochures and travel agents who disseminate information to consumers and have been relying on it to help them decide to plan and make their hotel choices (Varkaris & Neuhofer, 2017). According to a study by Alhaddad & Msallam (2016), an online community is where consumers share a common interest and purpose. Social media has also been considered as an electronic tool in conventional marketing and advertising scenarios (Gupta, 2019). He also added that it is a common platform for people to share content and open for discussions.

These may be determined as a very powerful tool that influences others to use or try something that they have shared-- the extension of word of mouth (Verma, 2018). It has changed how social media plays a big role in the traveler's choice in planning and decision making--the way tourists search and exchange information during the pre-travel stage (Gupta, 2019). Candidate tourists are also influenced by social media--with its content that other travelers share and how it can redirect their decisions (Varkaris & Neuhofer, 2017). Moreover, according to the study of Leung (2015), the supporting role of social media gives an impact of supporting the featured background of the hotel that could affect the relationship between social media and the client.

Social media has granted hotels and users to write comments and reviews showing that possible guests tend to rely on reviews and comments posted by other past guests of a hotel (Molinillo et al., 2016). By means of the contents posted by the hotel, this can be a vessel for people's opinions for a new promo the hotel is doing. They also stated that feedback from the past guests posted online influences the decision-making process of other possible clients. The feedback or recommendation from the guests are reviews from their past experience hence User Experience from the hotel, affecting other guests relying on feedback. With the continuous growth and development of social media to marketing and advertising, many consumers see social media as a trustworthy source of information and from everyone. However, there are Facebook.com, Twitter.com, and other consumer review sites that let their consumers and patron customers share their experience through comments and it has become a word of mouth that greatly influences other customers (Verma, 2018). She also added that social media has a notable impact on hotels as it attracts new clients and customers and retains the existing ones while increasing their online presence to customers.

Besides the fact that social media has been a known marketing tool for hotels, it has also been a platform and means for the hotels to communicate with their recent and potential customers and to understand their needs for them to provide it to their customers (Fadhil & Hashim, 2018). Since these hospitality products cannot be evaluated without consumption, these reviews create a significant role by influencing other people in review sites by sharing their opinions and experiences that makes others trustworthy to rely on their opinions, thus increasing their commitment to a particular brand (Alhaddad & Msallam, 2016). In addition to managing websites according to Leung and Bai (2015), a hotel should make their social media sites more interesting, appealing, informative, interactive and client centric so that guests and clients could enjoy and be convinced to book on creative management platforms.

The rapid increase of electronic WOM (word-of-mouth) can be traced because of the increase in the use of social media. As of Bai and Leung (2015), they have also stated that these word of mouth and electronic word-of-mouth or eWOM is very powerful in influencing guests' decisions, purchase intentions and customer loyalty.

Online reviews play a vital role in assisting consumers' evaluation stage, which provides positive and negative reviews and indirect customer-customer communication through the use of blogs and review sites (Varkaris & Neuhofer, 2017). According to a study in Varkaris & Neuhofer cited, hotel reviews are formed into probable choices and are influenced by mixed positive and negative reviews that raise awareness and can alter the reader's attitude towards hotel choices. Based on the study they found, when a hotel has negative comments on it, it is less likely for customers to book the hotel, while another study in their study shows that the one with a higher rating and great positive reviews, that hotel will most likely to accommodate guests and are an effective tool in purchasing their services. Since hotels have been utilizing social media, they are also using it to answer complaints, suggestions, and feedback (Fadhil & Hashim, 2018). They also offer special promotions, coupons, and something of monetary value to attract potential customers and benefit online community members who participate in these activities through social media (Alhaddad & Msallam, 2016).

Fadhil et al., (2018) also stated in their study that gifts can also act as the hotels' mechanism in attracting customers to be more active online. A Malaysian hotel is using this approach in his study to attract their customer engagements in their social media by highlighting the stay of some celebrity or famous people, thus creating more likes and it increases the hotel's online presence. As a result, the study shows that effective communication has always been concluded by the use of social media and how effective it would be if used towards entertaining clients to look after a hotel.

In addition to the content of social media sites of hotels, the quality of posts should also be recognized and managed. According to the study of Aluri et al., (2015), the travelers seeking entertainment gratifications during the initial visit should emphasize their expected enjoyment and entertainment that came primarily from the hotel's Social media websites. Prior to the content of their study, they also emphasized that hotel websites should always be certain on their post as it shows how the quality of the management and the hotel features on the web and how the clients would respond towards the information. Also they also emphasize that the key issue of hotel management is on how they would manage and understand what the client needs to be impressed or satisfied by just looking into the quality of the post which the hotel's website would provide. In addition to hotel websites, according to the study of Frankenstein, Joseph and Carley (2015), the management also needs to reconsider to conclude a better tool that could attract potential clients and reflect on the ratings of individuals reading and properly have the response to give such service towards the clients and potential guests.

In line towards the quality of post would be the Users Experience or generally their reviews from the hotel. Users' physical experience towards booking and being on the particular hotel gives a total impact in social media given that it emphasizes the quality service and management a hotel has. According to the study of Israel et al., (2019) states the direct and mediated presence of the client in which s/he experience during the present time at the hotel defines what they would review and thus the performance and quality compatible of the hotel's service is being observed. More so, the telepresence of perceived usefulness and perceived entertainment of the virtual hotel presentation are identical.

Lastly in social media websites, reaching people in terms of using social media platforms to easily access to see the content and entertained by the service and offers of hotels. According to Israel et al., (2019) the immerse understanding of social media sites by means of communication towards the clients and determines the immersive feeling of being there on the client and due to rapid technology progress continues to develop.

As what the Department of Tourism defined in their Memorandum Circular No. 2012-02 in Book One under General Provision, an accreditation is a certification regulated and issued by the Department as it recognizes the establishment complying or complied with its minimum standards posted by the authority for operating in tourism services and facilities (Jimenez, 2012). An accreditation is one of the levels and qualifications of the Department of Tourism.

Resort Hotels, as defined by Institute of Hotel Management Bhubaneswar in India (2017), are hotels that are located far from urban areas and have a very natural ambience and environment. The prices and rates depend on their services offered and additional services, usually ranging from moderate to high price. They are highly booked during vacation and weekends when people want to escape their daily routine. Some hotels are on a seasonal basis when operating but there are also hotels who operate all-year round. These resort hotels are luxurious accommodation facilities that offer full-service lodging facilities for relaxation for instance, beaches, ski parks and spas that provide sufficient and high-rating services to guests and these resort hotels include entertainment activities (Landman, 2020).

As much as the profile of the hotels are important, the demographics of the respondents in the study are also paramount for the researchers to gather their results. In a study by Aluri et al. (2015), those groups in younger years, specifically 18 to 24 years old are most likely to spend more time on social media than any other age groups and they believe that these groups might be the future general population. Nationality of the respondents are also essential in this study as of Al-Maslam, A. & Alhaddad, A. A. (2016), the response rate of the respondents depends on the vicinity of the respondents to the said subject hotels and that it could possibly be reliable.

Gender and age preferences of different room designs affect the intention of guests in a study of Bogicevic et al. (2018). According to their study, the demographics consider satisfaction as a part of experience in a design of a hotel room, Younger guests prefer a more present-day design while older guests show one and the same satisfaction to both present-day and traditional designs. In addition, according to Adiasih (2019), younger millennials are more prior to looking forward to what's the latest demands and latest trends and based on their finding in the age of 18 to 26 it is more reactable and more distinct in terms of what they would be looking for in a specific hotel. Lastly in terms of gender, based on their findings the span of females are the most likely to be active unlike the male in browsing social media for booking a hotel.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The proponents have used a correlational quantitative research design that tests the relationship of two variables without controlling either one of them (McCombes, 2019). Correlational research has been utilized in this study as it aims to study the statistical relationship between variables. "The basic design for correlational research involves a single group of people who are quantitatively measured on two (or more) characteristics (i.e. variables), that have already happened to them." (Sage Publications, 2016, p. 119). Also, the proponents used Descriptive Research Design to identify the demographic, and the effectiveness of Social Media from a volume of respondents.

B. Research Sampling Method

The researchers used Purposive Sampling Method or 'Deliberate Sampling' wherein the samples are picked and or selected based on their judgment and the most useful according to the needs of the study (Glen, 2015). It is a nonrandom technique that does not need underlying studies for participants. The researchers decide and find people who are willing to provide the information needed for the study (Etikan, 2016). Additionally, homogenous sampling focuses on respondents with the same characteristics or features, for example, they may be identical in age or occupations. It is for the purpose of their similarity and how it applies to the subject of the study. The researchers gathered 323 respondents for the approximately 2000 population needed in the said three hotel establishments.

C. Data Gathering and Analysis

The research was done in Tagaytay where the hotel establishments are located. The proponents have decided that the respondents for the study would be the previous guests who left reviews of the hotel establishments and were contacted through the official Facebook page of the hotel establishments, Agoda page reviews dated from 2019 and above, of the establishments and were given the online survey forms for them to answer.

The proponents used an online survey and used Google Forms as a platform that contained all the survey forms and responses from all respondents since the scope of the study fell during this time of pandemic. 4-point Likert scale is used in the questionnaire since it also offers collection of data which is organized into a scaled hierarchy. Considering the 4-point Likert Scale in the study because it gives the assumption on the "survey of opinions" in which the key assumption would be present in getting the needed data from the guest, according to the study of Joshi (2015). Hence, this concept gives the topic a more distinct and explanatory and it helps the aim of researchers to measure their proposed topic.

Upon getting in contact with the respondents, an Informed Consent was provided to them to confirm their participation in the study and protect their anonymity. Once their Informed Consent is signed, the research questionnaire was sent. Once all responses are gathered, the researchers have analyzed the data using Pearson Correlation Coefficient to test whether the factors (quality of post, user experiences and people reached) have a significant relationship with the effectiveness of social media.

Pearson correlation coefficient is a test statistic that measures the relationship among two continuous variables. It aims to measure the strength of the association between the variables and map out the direction of their relationship (*Pearson's Correlation Coefficient* 2020). The range of the results will vary from -1, having Perfect Negative Correlation, to +1, having Perfect Positive Correlation (*Pearson Product-Moment Correlation* 2018). The researchers are guided by a Statistician for accurate analysis of the data using a program.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Demographic Profile of the respondents

1.1 Hotel

Table 1.1: Demographic

Hotel Resort	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Hotel A	147	45.5	1
Hotel B	120	37.2	2
Hotel C	56	17.3	3
Total	323	100.0	

Figure 1.1 shows, among the three (3) subject hotels, 45.5% of the respondents answered Hotel A with the frequency of 147 compared to the other subject hotels--Hotel B with the frequency of 120 and 37.2% and Hotel C with the frequency of 56 and 17.3%. Hotel A got the most frequency and highest percentage since they have almost 80,000 likes compared to the other hotels

1.2 Age

Table 1.2: Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
18-26 yr old	121	37.5	1
45-53 yr old	90	27.9	2
27-35 yr old	58	18.0	3
36-44 yr old	53	16.4	4
54 yr old and above	1	0.3	5
Total	323	100.0	

Figure 1.2 reveals that among the 323 respondents the researchers gathered, 18-26 years old are the highest ones who usually booked at these hotels with a frequency of 121 and 37.5% and marked as the highest outcome. A study by Aluri (2015) and Gupta (2019), states that in modern times, younger generations are prone to adapt faster in managing social media in choosing their hotel. Also, the capability of the younger generation in choosing their hotel would be from social media sources as compared to older respondents wherein they prefer the conventional hotel booking. A mix of Millennials and Generation Z is the largest part of the demographics by age which also had the biggest contribution in the proponent's study because those Generations are the ones who got hit by the development of technology through the times. The effectiveness of social media dictates also the development of technologies that eases the long process of bookings to short pre-made messages. Gupta (2015) also mentioned that Instagram is now an important part in playing with the decision-making of the consumers as it is viewed as an app that provides pictures, videos, and links that are related to their prior travel. He also mentioned in his study that these age groups are readily available and provide a maximum response. Conversely, the group with the lowest percentage of 0.3 % are 54 years old and above with a frequency of 1 which also states from the study of Gupta V. (2019) because they are more likely to have a low possibility to distinguish the latest trends and suitable room that they would be capable with instead they ask for assistance to younger people to assist them to their need. As per the study of Chang et al., (2019) older people are discerned more of the complexity of technology than younger people and

may need a user guide when accessing hotel reservations. Conversely, the younger people associate frequent use of the Internet and are more likely to book an online reservation in the hotel.

1.3 Gender

Table 1.3: Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Female	121	37.5	1
Male	58	18.0	2
Total	323	100.0	

Figure 1.3 reveals that the demographic representation of respondents with a total of 323 and with the classification of the highest percentage is the females with a frequency of 182 and a percentage of 56.3%. Based on the results, the female has the majority results that imply females are most likely to be active in browsing social media and to engage in online bookings and reservations. Also, they are perceived to be more responsible in planning the accommodations for a trip. The variance of the roles of responsibility between female and male varies wherein the females are more often responsible in planning whilst males are more into the services and experiences they would be getting in the hotel such as parking, Wi-Fi, and personal services for customers. In a study by Chang et al. (2019), they stated that females are perceived to be more useful than males in engaging in social media platforms, and more likely to accept and try online reservations if there is, and it helps them identify the rooms they want in a hotel quickly.

On the other hand, the lowest percentage are the males with a frequency of 141 and a percent of 43.7%. Hence, the significance of respondents is showing that the females are active prior in answering the survey while the male has a lower count. Whilst females are into planning, males intended to be more critical of the hotel's equipment, room services, and maintenance. In result, this factor can greatly affect the study by differentiating the most active browsers from those that are based on tangible experience. Thus, in a study of Aluri (2015) when it comes to demographic reconsideration, almost 66% of their respondents were female and have given a more refined and detailed response towards their study than male respondents.

1.4 Nationality

Table 1.4 Nationality

Nationality	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Filipino	319	98.8	1
Others	5	1.5	2
Total	323	100.0	

Figure 1.4 reveals that the majority of the respondents are of Filipino nationality with 98.8% and frequency of 319 whilst the rest of the respondents are of other nationality with 1.5%. In relation to the data, in the study of Al-Maslam, A. & Alhaddad, A. A. (2016) expected to have the highest rate or percentage with survey questionnaires within the vicinity would be local tourists given the cause that these respondents have the most possible and reliable source of data in which they could easily gather. The response rate of the respondents affects the hotel page since the rate of respondents depends on the location of the subject hotels. Also, given the fact of the COVID-19 pandemic the usual guests that book hotels are Filipinos. The nationality of the respondents is also essential in this study as according to Al-Maslam, A. & Alhaddad, A. A. (2016), the response rate of the respondents depends on the vicinity of the respondents to the said subject hotels and that it could possibly be reliable.

On the other hand, as the lowest frequency and percentage in the category would be other nationalities as it implies that the hotel establishment caters more to local residents and tourists than other citizens with different nationalities. As the study has been done during the pandemic, the factors regarding the restrictions and limitations are considered since travel bans are not yet lifted to certain parts and other protocols and policies are being made by the Department of Tourism. Hence, with the protocol that has been brought down by the Department of Tourism, hotels are following the health protocol with regards to accepting guests from other countries and should strictly observe the guidelines in accordance to the memorandum.

1.5 Purpose of Stay

Figure 1.5: Purpose of Stay

Purpose of Stay	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Leisure	293	90.7	1
Work	30	9.3	2
Total	323	100.0	

Figure 1.5 reveals that the majority (90.7%) of the respondents booked hotels for their leisure time with a frequency of 293 whilst the latter booked for work purposes. The result shows that most respondents book hotels in the purpose of leisure as the highest percentage data and work purposes as the lowest and in the reason that hotels have been engaging to invigorate their promotions with regards to amenities and facilities with the sole purpose of leisure but taking considerations of the guests who book particularly for work purposes. Most people who post on social media with a picture of a hotel they booked influence other guests to book for the purpose of leisure with their relatives.

In the study of Neuhofer, B., & Varkaris, E. (2017) considering that the influence of social media has affected well the perspective of the guest in booking in which he or she had a glimpse of what has ahead to be shown if they were to experience it together with the factor that they would bring their families, relatives, etc. is a bigger impact for them to enjoy leisure. However, the work for their purpose of stay got only 9.3% and a frequency of 30. The working phase is that it only tackles the idea of having a venue for a specific work-related activity for instances: *Seminars, Conference, Work travels, and Company Outings* in which in the study of Gupta, V. (2019) says that companies intended to canvas hotels with the required vicinity and environment for their agenda and with the help of social media they would have the option with a wide variation of reviews that would benefit their decision in comes of the vicinity, price, and accommodation stated on the study of Andres (2016).

1.6 Gross Annual Income

Table 1.6: Gross Annual Income

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Not over P250,000	199	61.6	1
Over P400,000	115	35.6	2
Over P800,000 but not over P 2,000,000	9	2.8	3
Total	323	100.0	

Figure 1.6 shows that the majority of the respondents have an income of not over Php 250,000 with 61.6% and frequency of 199 and the lowest of the respondents have an income of over Php 800,000 but not over 2M with 2.8%. Mostly because the majority of the respondents are 18-26 years old and on an entry job if they are currently working. The result implies the study by taking the budget of their usual clients and guests into consideration and adjusting their pricing of the services and accommodation rates. Although the industry would be having a hard time since the pandemic began, their annual income would be the primary influence in their budget for booking in hotels.

However, in a study by Adiasih et. al (2019), the income of any consumer or guests is not a variable that determines their disposition to consume any products and services from the hotel. The results showed lowest income of not over Php 800,000 but not over 2M with 2.8% posting and enhancing luxurious amenities and features of the hotel could make future high-paying guests book the establishment. Also, additional exclusivity promotions can also be promoted to capture the interest of the guests in the category.

1.7 Time spent on social media

Table 1.7: Time spent in Social Media

Hotel Resort	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
4-6 hours	185	57.3	1
1-3 hours	98	30.3	2
7-9 hours	40	12.4	3
Total	323	100.0	

Figure 1.7 shows that the majority of the respondents spend 4-6 hours on social media with 57.3% and frequency of 185 as a result of having the highest percentage. Based on the study of Sarla, G. S. (2020) that people often use social media on a monetary basis wherein 4 - 6 hours is the prescribed usage to be able to ensure the health of the eyes. The result implies that the new generation browse everything on social media as it is the future potential guests of the hotels. It is ample time to check out promos, posts, and other promotional content of hotels that may determine some of the effectiveness of hotel pages.

On the other hand, the lowest accumulated percentage was only 12.4% on 7-9 hours daily. A study by Sarla, G. S. (2020) states that exposure to too much radiation from gadgets would greatly affect the eyesight of an individual. Given to which it might cause damage to the eye it may also reconsider to have a longer variation of opinions in surfing toward social media platforms in which in the study of Almutawa, H. (2019) states that the wide variation of social media marketing would catch the interest of one individual that takes time to satisfy and conclude their needs in a vicinity of a hotel.

Verbal Interpretation of the Mean

1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree/Very Low
1.50-2.49	Disagree/Low
2.50-3.49	Agree/High
3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree/Very High

2.1. Quality Content of the posts

A. Quality or content of the posts	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The photos posted online are attractive to me as a tourist.	3.52	0.54	Strongly Agree	2
The posts include the contact information of the establishment	3.54	0.51	Strongly Agree	1
The posts gave exact directions and landmarks for the hotel's location.	3.51	0.52	Strongly Agree	3
The photos posted are repeating or outdated.	3.16	0.76	Agree	10
The posts translate to what it looks like in person.	3.43	0.53	Agree	6
The posts feature the expected services and facilities of the hotel.	3.46	0.52	Agree	4
The sponsored content or posts means the establishment is prominent or well-known.	3.40	0.52	Agree	8
The posts do feature, or share mentions from satisfied customers/clients.	3.41	0.53	Agree	7
The hotel's peak hours displayed in their page makes me choose other hotels instead that are less crowded.	3.27	0.65	Agree	9
The posts of the hotel in their social media are polite to their guests when it comes to responding to the guests' queries.	3.44	0.53	Agree	5
Overall Assessment on the Effectiveness Social Media in terms of QUALITY/CONTENT	3.415	0.38	High	

This table shows that the highest rank that accumulated a mean of 3.54 wherein respondents strongly agree that the posts shows the contact of the establishments may it be a website, email they can contact or telephone and or mobile number. Being ranked as high rank, the post that shows the contact of the establishments may be a website, email has an extensive impact on the study in which it signifies as the quality of the management of the hotel. People would also think that the hotel is reliable and can accommodate their needs. According to Aluri et al. (2015), hotel establishments should be precise on the posts they publish since it exhibits the quality of the management the hotel has and how the guests can acknowledge the posted information.

However, the lowest rank accumulated a mean of 3.16 wherein the respondents disagree on the posts being repeated or outdated by the establishments. Repeating posts may be a negative influence in the pre-booking stage of a potential guest as the website may seem neglected and posts aren't updated by the management, thus a lack of marketing to sell the establishment's products and services. In a study by Frankenstein et al., (2015), the management should think of considering other tools and methods to attract guests and that it may reflect on their ratings. Overall, the quality of posts by the establishments garnered a mean of 3.41 with verbal interpretation of High.

2.2 User Experience

USER EXPERIENCE	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Social media helps me to look and decide on what hotel is more popular and consistent for good reviews.	3.54	0.55	Strongly Agree	1
Social media for me is a reliable source for hotel reviews and content.	3.47	0.55	Agree	2
The reviews on the hotels are unbiased.	3.30	0.58	Agree	10
The experience and comments of reviewers are 100% reliable in booking a hotel.	3.39	0.53	Agree	7
The rating of the reviews affect my decision in booking for a hotel.	3.41	0.53	Agree	5
The experience of the previous guests are somehow parallel to the experience one had.	3.36	0.52	Agree	9
The social media gave a brief outlook and peek on what the guest can experience in their offered services.	3.40	0.51	Agree	6
Social media is a great tool for people to voice out their experiences.	3.45	0.52	Agree	3
Social media pages of the hotels are very responsive to messages.	3.36	0.55	Agree	8
Using social media star rating of a hotel to choose a hotel.	3.44	0.52	Agree	4
Overall Assessment on the Effectiveness Social Media in terms of USER EXPERIENCE	3.411	0.38	High	

This table shows that the highest rank that accumulated a mean of 3.54 where respondents strongly agree that social media helps them to look and decide on what hotel establishment is popular and rational on good reviews which increases the probability of new guests. User experience enhances the probability of new guests by looking and filtering the reviews of past guests affects the effectiveness of good reviews of the hotel. Also the following or popularity of the hotel plays a big role in measuring the effectiveness of social media of the establishment by greatly affecting the decision-making process of new guests. The following that the hotel page has also affects the decision of possible guests. According to a study of Varkaris and Neuhofer (2017), the probable choices of the guests are influenced by the mixed positive and negative reviews that can alter their choices.

The lowest rank gathered a mean of 3.30 wherein the respondents agree that the reviews on the hotels are unbiased. Based on the result, the hotel was able to control and filter out the reviews that can be shown in their respective pages. According to the study of He et al. (2017), it is important that the hotel collect, monitor, analyze, summarize, and visualize online guest reviews posted on social media that could shed light for possible guests of their experience, opinions, feelings and concerns. Overall, the user experience garnered a mean of 3.41 with the verbal interpretation of High.

2.3 People Reached

PEOPLE REACHED	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Social media helps hotels to address guest inquiries faster.	3.49	0.537	Agree	2
The social media can immediately transport the guest to the hotel's website to check for other offers.	3.43	0.561	Agree	7
Social media helps hotels reach people by means of sponsored posts.	3.45	0.528	Agree	5
Social media helps hotels reach people by means of recreational video interface and entertainment.	3.43	0.544	Agree	8
Social media aids in capturing attention to view the hotel's page.	3.44	0.503	Agree	6
Social media reviews tend to boost a hotel's page to attract guests.	3.46	0.511	Agree	4
Social media is a tool for dissemination of information regarding hotel's deals and bookings.	3.47	0.524	Agree	3
The hotel's following and likes of posts determines the effectiveness of social media towards the hotel.	3.41	0.524	Agree	9
The hotel's followers boost the potential guests' interest to avail their accredited services.	3.41	0.510	Agree	10
Social media is a great tool for the hotels to enlarge their community activities and engagements.	3.50	0.525	Strongly Agree	1
Overall Assessment on the Effectiveness Social Media in terms of PEOPLE REACHED	3.449	0.3890	High	

The table shows that the highest rank that accumulated a mean of 3.50 where respondents strongly agree that social media is a great tool for the hotels to enlarge their community activities and engagements. The high rank shows the large potential of the effectiveness of social media by making engaging activities for potential online guests. According to the study of Alhaddad & Msallam (2016), a Malaysian Hotel highlighted the stay of a celebrity to enlarge their hotels' online presence. They also stated that hotels offer promotions and coupons to attract potential customers.

As for the low rank, proponents gathered a mean of 3.41 wherein the respondents disagree that the engagements of the hotels are responsive to their needs. Based on the result, the hotel establishment failed to respond quicker to the inquiries of their potential guests. The audience the hotels have in social media helps gain the attention of potential guests making social media a tool for gathering more guests. Overall, the people reached garnered a mean of 3.44 with a verbal interpretation of High.

3.1 Is there a significant relationship between the factors (quality of post, user experiences, and people reached) that measures the effectiveness of social media?

Correlations		QUALITY/CONTENT	USER EXPERIENCE	PEOPLE REACHED
QUALITY/CONTENT	Pearson Correlation	1	.665**	.644**
	p-value		0.000	0.000
USER EXPERIENCE	Pearson Correlation	.665**	1	.703**
	p-value	0.000		0.000
PEOPLE REACHED	Pearson Correlation	.644**	.703**	1
	p-value	0.000	0.000	

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The gathered data on the degree of significance showed that there is a significant positive relationship between the factors: quality of post and user experiences, since the Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient of 0.665 has a p-value less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. The result indicated higher assessment of the quality of post would most likely indicate higher assessment on user experiences and vice versa.

There is a significant and positive relationship between the factors: quality of post and people reached since Pearson's Correlation Coefficient of 0.644 has a p-value less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. The result indicated higher assessment of the quality of post would most likely indicate higher assessment on people reached and vice versa. There is a significant and positive relationship between the factors: user experiences and people reached, since Pearson's Correlation Coefficient of 0.703 has a p-value less than 0.05. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected. The result indicated higher assessment of the user experiences would most likely indicate higher assessment on people reached and vice versa.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results the researchers gathered, the following conclusions were drawn wherein the researchers found out that Hotel A is the leading hotel wherein the respondents have been with 18-26 years old visitors wherein being in the younger generations has its adaptive and modern idealization of demands wherein the Gen Z could briefly identify what are the latest trend and stipulations on booking a hotel so thus social media is their aid for the job and also Generation Z are the ones who have adequate knowledge of using social media brought by the ceaseless changes in the growing technological world. The result also revealed mostly Filipino nationality with the purpose of leisure more than work. In view of that, the nearby tourists and guests are the ones who have more access in booking the subject establishments and also since the industry is facing a difficult time in admitting guests especially the foreign ones. The respondents also responded leisure over work given that the hotels promote and endorse mostly on their leisure amenities and promotions that are best consumed on leisure time. This has shown that hotels posting their featured amenities have been constructive on the choices of their potential guests. An income of not over Php 250,000 has shown larger responses as it matches with the ages 18-16 year old respondents who usually book hotels. The people who are in the said age brackets have entry jobs that earns them an income of not over Php250,000 a year since the majority of the respondents are on the span of young adults up to adults that have their own prospective jobs budgeting is also a factor in their expenses. The basis of not over Php 250,000 is the assumed budget for booking a hotel. The existing budget of the young adults would act as a limit on how much expenses they can afford towards a hotel establishment. It also showed that the majority of the respondents spent an average of 4 to 6 hours on social media daily. The result revealed that the majority of the respondents take about 4-6 hours a day browsing

through social media that gave them sufficient time to browse through the hotel's features on their social media pages. The amount of time spent of the respondents reflects that social media is an effective platform for hotel establishments to post their promotions. The results also showed that there are more female respondents booking the hotel establishments compared to male respondents. These exhibits show that females are more likely to browse on social media and update themselves about the promotions and also are likely to express and share one's experience. Females are also perceived to be involved in the planning stage whilst the males are into the intangible services of the hotel establishments. Therefore, the proponents conclude that social media is fully utilized by younger generations of female Filipinos who influence the upcoming and older generations to use the ease of using social media. Therefore, social media integrates its ease of access and tools to hotel establishments for the use of their prospective guests in the social media world used commonly these days.

In answering the second statement of the problem, the researchers found that the respondents strongly agree that the posts of the establishment have presented and included their contact information be it any website, contact number and or email that the guests can reach to book in their hotel. Potential guests would choose to stay in hotel establishments that they think can accommodate their needs and they think are reliable enough. It shows that the management of the hotel establishment is consistent with the service they offer to their prospective guests who check their website and unvaried updates. Hence, hotels should also be aware of the importance of the content represented on social media to make sure that their actions lead to the generation of positive content through close social circles to the consumers while minimizing negative and addressing inexistent content by facilitating the generation of comprehensive content which helps the consumers in making their informative decision towards booking their hotel choice. Also, hotel establishments who present their contact information on the posts they publish are more likely to be booked since it exhibits ease of access, convenience, and faster transactions for the guests thus creating more profit and sales for the hotels. They also depend on social media to be one click away from all their needs and demands to be fulfilled. The proponents conclude that social media pages of the hotels include the contact of the establishment that makes the people rely on and it shows that the hotel establishment is exceptional in giving out updated posts.

In terms of User Experiences, the researchers found out that the respondents strongly agree that social media helps them decide and look for hotels that are popular and logical in terms of good reviews. The usual users of social media relies on the electronic word-of-mouth that is circulating around a website or page and a good set of reviews helps the hotel establishments' page and or website boost within their target market and to achieve their target sales, that influences the customers loyalty and decisions and purchasing intentions. Reviews are a crucial part of the pre-booking stage of a guest, as they determine their choices in booking any hotel establishment. Therefore, the proponents conclude that potential guests interested in booking an establishment through social media relied mostly on reviews posted on their respective social media pages affecting their decision making process to book.

And lastly, the researchers found out that the respondents strongly agree that social media is a great tool for building a larger community and being more engaging to other potential guests, as social media today is a vast representation of how fast the transaction of communication varies. In recent studies, people intend to notice prior management excellence if the hotel itself replies or answers the needs and questions ahead and is able to give resolution towards their thoughts. Another factor is that the connection and the relationship between the hotel and guest can affect with its parameter of length of information. With the use of social media platforms, the hotel's reach of information is widely increased to be noticed by potential guests that could gain more attraction by means of using the word of mouth sequence. The proponents conclude that social media pages of the hotels reached multiple people and or communities by sharing posts, investing in sponsored posts which will advertise the hotel's promotional posts, and also engaging with other guests' comments and reviews.

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